

Resource-and-Latency-Aware PSO — A novel algorithm for intelligent and contextual cloud native resource scheduling

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Abstract—Swarm Intelligence (SI) has emerged as a prominent approach in resource scheduling, offering adaptability and effectiveness in multi-objective optimisation. However, SI-based methods often introduce complexity and challenges such as premature convergence and excessive exploration, leading to suboptimal performance. To address these challenges, this paper presents a novel Resource-and-Latency-Aware Particle Swarm Optimisation (RALA-PSO) algorithm for intelligent and contextual cloud native resource scheduling. RALA-PSO expands upon Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) by incorporating a greedy initialisation for faster convergence, a circular search space to avoid boundary stagnation, a multi-criteria fitness function tailored to Cloud-Native characteristics, a heuristic-based scoring model to reward suitable solutions, and the integration of adaptive weights and learning factors for exploration–exploitation balance. The RALA-PSO implementation is available as open-source in [14]. RALA-PSO prioritises solutions based on efficient resource allocation and less communication overhead via service co-location. Experimental evaluations using the Alibaba Cluster TraceV2018 dataset show that RALA-PSO reduces network transmission overhead cost by 1.8× to 2.36× compared to state-of-the-art algorithms MOPPSO-CMS and ACO-CMS, while maintaining competitive resource efficiency. Notably, RALA-PSO achieves runtimes up to 212 times faster than ACO-CMS and 1.5 times faster than MOPPSO-CMS. These results demonstrate that RALA-PSO is a scalable, efficient, and context-aware scheduling solution for cloud-native applications, particularly effective in environments with strict network and resource constraints.

Index Terms—Swarm Intelligence, resource scheduling, cloud-native and edge

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent works in cloud-native scheduling and optimisation have explored Swarm Intelligence (SI) due to its flexibility in handling non-linear, discrete, and dynamic environments, conditions which traditional algebraic methods often struggle with. Unlike Machine Learning (ML), which relies on datasets and training, SI algorithms’ population-based design and support for multi-objective optimisation without assumptions about the objective function suggest they might be well-suited for edge and cloud. Nevertheless, SI methods often entail increased algorithmic complexity and may suffer from premature convergence and excessive exploration. To address these,

we propose the Resource-and-Latency-Aware Particle Swarm Optimisation (RALA-PSO) algorithm that optimises resource allocation and minimises communication overhead via service co-location. RALA-PSO enhances traditional Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) through five key innovations: a greedy initialisation for faster convergence, a circular search space to avoid boundary stagnation, a multi-criteria fitness function that considers Cloud-Native characteristics, a heuristic-based scoring model to reward suitable solutions, and the integration of adaptive weights and learning factors for a more balanced exploration-exploitation trade-off. These enhancements are not jointly present in existing PSO variants, which typically optimise only resource usage or Pareto fronts. Their integration enables dependency-aware, latency-driven placement and distinguishes RALA-PSO from prior adaptations. This paper presents the design and evaluation of RALA-PSO. The paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews SI-based algorithms. Section III introduces our proposed solution. Section IV shows the experiments conducted and results obtained. Section V concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews SI approaches for resource scheduling. SI refers to a class of biologically inspired algorithms that use stochastic search processes and iterative cooperative heuristics to explore and exploit complex solution spaces collectively. Examples include PSO, based on avian flocking behaviour [3], and Ant Colony Optimisation (ACO), based on pheromone-driven foraging in ants [4]. Both have been used for application scheduling in edge and cloud, where the problem is typically formulated as a multi-objective optimisation task. For instance, Lin et al. [4] proposed the ACO-MCMS algorithm with three objectives: reducing network transmission overhead between microservices, balancing cluster load, and enhancing the reliability of cluster services. Nevertheless, ACO-MCMS exhibits a time complexity of $O(N_{\max} \times K \times n^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^m \text{Scale}_i)$, where N_{\max} is the maximum number of iterations, K is the size of the ant colony, n is the number of nodes in the cluster, and $\sum_{i=1}^m \text{Scale}_i$ represents the total of microservice

replicas. This complexity can be prohibitive for real-time scheduling scenarios, as performance degrades quadratically with microservice, node, or request growth. To overcome the limitations of ACO-MCMS, X. Chen et al. [3] proposed a new approach, MOPPSO-CMS, which combines the fast convergence and parallelism of PSO with Pareto dominance. Although MOPPSO-CMS demonstrates improved performance, its complexity still pose challenges related to scalability, parameter sensitivity, and the balance between exploration and exploitation, which hinder the efficiency in large-scale, dynamic environments [2], [5], [6]. Our approach extends the original PSO [7], considering the cloud-native context (cf. Section III). To contextualise our proposal, we begin by summarising essential PSO concepts. A particle is a candidate solution whose position marks a point in the search space. Each particle maintains two key values: the personal best $p_{kbest,i}$, denoting the best solution it has discovered so far, and the global best $g_{best,i}$, denoting the best solution identified by any particle in the entire swarm. The particle's position is updated by adding its velocity to its current position, as described in Eq. (1).

$$X_k(i+1) = X_k(i) + V_k(i+1) \quad (1)$$

Where $X_k(i)$ represents the current position of particle k at iteration i , $X_k(i+1)$ the updated position at iteration $i+1$, and $V_k(i+1)$ corresponds to the velocity of particle k at iteration $i+1$. Velocity governs how a particle moves through the search space to find optimal solutions. The velocity accounts for the particle's current position $X_k(i)$, its personal best position $p_{kbest,i}$ and the global best position $g_{best,i}$ with coefficients c_1 and c_2 controlling the influence of the personal and global bests (Eq. (2), from Eberhart et al. [8]).

$$V_k(i+1) = wV_k(i) + c_1r_1\Delta p_k(i) + c_2r_2\Delta g_k(i) \quad (2)$$

r_1 and r_2 are random numbers in $[0, 1]$, $\Delta p_k(i) = p_{b,i} - X_k(i)$ denote the displacement from personal best and $\Delta g_k(i) = g_{b,i} - X_k(i)$ the displacement from the global best. The population comprises all particles, each representing a candidate solution that is iteratively updated through changes in velocity and position. The algorithm begins by randomly initialising these positions and velocities. During each iteration, velocities and positions are updated based on the personal and global best values. The fitness of each particle is then evaluated through an objective function, with personal and global bests updated whenever improved solutions are found. This process continues until convergence or termination, with the final population representing the scheduling decision.

III. RESOURCE-AND-LATENCY-AWARE PSO (RALA-PSO)

We propose a novel algorithm: Resource-and-Latency-Aware Particle Swarm Optimisation (RALA-PSO) as an enhanced PSO variant designed for the constraints of dynamic, cloud-native environments. RALA-PSO, available as open-source in [14], maintains the simplicity and lightweight nature

of traditional PSO, while introducing five novel enhancements (see Section III-B), enabling intelligent, context-aware scheduling. The following sections describe the design of RALA-PSO, covering the system model, particle initialisation, evolution and fitness function.

A. System Model

We defined the optimal placement by two equally important criteria: (1) selecting clusters with more available resources (i.e., lower current usage), minimising the distance between interdependent components (i.e., frequently communicating components). We assume single-node clusters with co-located replicas, which simplifies modelling and suits horizontally scaled deployments. This assumption, however, limits generalisability to more distributed and fault-tolerant systems where replicas are spread across nodes.

$$\langle \mathcal{R} \mid \mathcal{A} \rangle \quad (3)$$

The model takes as input a tuple (Eq. (3)), consisting of: \mathcal{R} , a tuple of available clusters to schedule; \mathcal{A} , the set of requested applications deployment.

$$\mathcal{R} \rightarrow \langle \mathcal{C}_{id} \mid \mathcal{C}_{spec} \rangle \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{C}_{spec} \rightarrow \langle \mathcal{A}_x \mid \mathcal{T}_x \rangle \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{X} \rightarrow \langle CPU; DSK; RAM \rangle \quad (6)$$

The \mathcal{A}_{spec} (Eq. (7)) includes \mathcal{A}_{id} as the application identifier, \mathcal{A}_{req} detailing the application's resource requirements, and \mathcal{L} representing network requirements and interdependencies.

$$\mathcal{A}_{spec} \rightarrow \langle \mathcal{A}_{id} \mid \mathcal{A}_{req} \mid \mathcal{L} \rangle \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_{req} \rightarrow \langle \mathcal{M}_{id} \mid \mathcal{R}_x \mid \mathcal{CONS} \mid \mathcal{R}_{set} \rangle \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{L} \rightarrow \langle \mathcal{T}_{req} \mid \mathcal{R}_{thr} \mid \mathcal{D}_{trans} \mid \mathcal{T}_{time} \mid \mathcal{D}_{ist} \rangle \quad (9)$$

\mathcal{A}_{req} (Eq. (8)) defines resource requirements \mathcal{R}_x per component and replica count \mathcal{R}_{set} . The \mathcal{L} set (Eq. (9)) includes total requests \mathcal{T}_{req} (as tuple $\langle \mathcal{M}_{id} \mid \mathcal{M}_{id} \rangle$), request threshold \mathcal{R}_{thr} , data volume \mathcal{D}_{trans} , transmission time \mathcal{T}_{time} , and component distance \mathcal{D}_{ist} .

RALA-PSO defines the fundamental PSO unit, particle (Eq. (10)), which is the optimisation construct used by the PSO algorithm to explore candidate placement solutions. Each particle includes \mathcal{P} as the assigned cluster, \mathcal{V} as the velocity controlling search direction and speed, \mathcal{F} as the current solution quality, and $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{P}}$ and $\mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{F}}$ as the particle's best position and fitness to date.

$$\langle \mathcal{P} \mid \mathcal{V} \mid \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{P}} \mid \mathcal{F} \mid \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{F}} \rangle \quad (10)$$

B. Design Principles and Algorithm

RALA-PSO retains PSO's advantages, including the ability to handle constrained and multi-objective optimisation problems and the simplicity afforded by its minimal parameter requirements. Furthermore, RALA-PSO introduces five key enhancements to the standard PSO algorithm:

- The incorporation of a greedy approach combined with probabilistic reasoning (cf. Section III-C), employed during population initialisation to ensure particles start in feasible (or at least sub-optimal) positions.
- A circular search space used to prevent particles from becoming trapped at the minimum or maximum boundaries (cf. Section III-D).
- A multi-objective fitness function to balance multiple criteria of resource scheduling (cf. Section III-E).
- A heuristic method for classifying cluster suitability.
- Integration of adaptive weights (Eq. (11)) and learning factors (Eqs. (12) and (13)) adapted from [12].

Algorithm 1 RALA-PSO Algorithm

Require: $\langle \mathcal{R} \mid \mathcal{A} \rangle$, global parameters

Ensure: Optimal component location (by maximising fitness function)

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1:  $BestFitness \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $solution \leftarrow None$ 
3: for each execution  $e = 1$  to  $N_{executions}$  do
4:   for each component do
5:     Identify feasible clusters (fulfil application resources requirements)
6:     Compute allocation scores considering constraints
7:     Assign initial position based on larger allocation score
8:     Update clusters' resources availability considering the initial position
9:   end for
10:  for each iteration  $i = 1$  to  $max_{iterations}$  do
11:    Update inertia weight  $w$  and learning factors  $c_1, c_2$ 
12:    Check feasibility of current particle allocation
13:    for each particle do
14:      Update velocity ( $v$ ) and position ( $p$ )
15:      Evaluate fitness particle
16:      Update local and global bests if improved
17:    end for
18:  end for
19:  Evaluate fitness of current solution
20:  if current fitness  $\geq BestFitness$  then
21:     $BestFitness \leftarrow$  current fitness
22:     $solution \leftarrow$  current particle positions
23:  end if
24: end for
25: return  $Solution, BestFitness$ 

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RALA-PSO (Algorithm 1) begins by initialising the best fitness value ($best_{fitness}$) and the best solution. To reduce the inherent stochastic variability of PSO and improve the chances of finding a high-quality global solution, it performs multiple independent executions ($N_{executions}$, line 3). The algorithm starts by initialising the particle (see Section III-C). This entails identifying feasible clusters, scoring them, assigning each component to a cluster probabilistically based on these scores (simulating an allocation), and updating cluster resources accordingly (lines 5–8). During each iteration ($max_{iterations}$), the algorithm updates each particle (cf. Section III-D), which includes adjusting the inertia weight (w) and learning factors (c_1, c_2) to balance exploration and exploitation, evaluating the feasibility of the current solution (i.e. assess if cluster have resources to fulfil the application requirements), and updating the particle's velocity and position (lines 11–14). After that,

the particle's fitness is evaluated (cf. Section III-E), and if a better position is found, the corresponding best values are updated (line 16). At the end of each execution, the algorithm evaluates the fitness of the current solution, i.e., the fitness of all particles. If this fitness is greater than or equal to the best fitness recorded so far, it updates the global best fitness and the corresponding solution (lines 21–22). After completing all executions, the algorithm returns the best solution along with its fitness value (line 25).

C. Particle Swarm Initialisation

Unlike the random cluster selection in the original PSO, we introduce a greedy and probabilistic method for particle initialisation. The greedy aspect ensures particles are initialised within feasible regions of the search space, meaning components are assigned only to clusters that meet application requirements (Eq. (8) with available resources (Eq. (6)). Moreover, the probabilistic approach computes allocation scores, enabling components to be placed in higher-scoring clusters with greater probability rather than always selecting the single best option deterministically. It is worth noting that this strategy reduces initial diversity compared to random sampling, as choices are biased toward higher scores, limiting exploration in some cases. This introduces extra computational overhead during initialisation compared to random sampling. Nevertheless, in Cloud-Native environments, prioritising feasibility and resource-aware preferences is generally more beneficial than complete randomness, as it accelerates convergence toward valid and high-quality solutions. Hence, combining greedy and probabilistic initialisation reduces the risk of infeasible or poor-quality initial placements while still maintaining enough diversity to prevent premature convergence. The allocation score is a weighted sum of the Resource-Aware and the Constraint-Aware scores, each contributing 50%. The Resource-Aware score measures a cluster's attractiveness based on its available resources, favouring those with greater remaining capacity. The Constraint-Aware score incentivises clusters that have already been initialised and host components on which the current particle depends, encouraging co-location and reducing potential inter-component latency. These scores are normalised using a softmax function, ensuring clusters with higher scores have proportionally greater chances of being chosen, while still allowing exploration of other feasible options.

D. Particle Evolution

In RALA-PSO, particle evolution is enhanced through the introduction of adaptive inertia weights (w) and learning factors (c_1, c_2). Specifically, RALA-PSO adopts the adaptive weight mechanism from Eq. (11) and the dynamic learning factors defined in Eq. (12) and Eq. (13), initially proposed by Liu et al. [12]. This novel integration enables the algorithm to dynamically balance exploration and exploitation during the search, preventing premature convergence and improving the ability to escape local optima. Hence, RALA-PSO achieves faster convergence and higher-quality scheduling solutions.

$$\omega(t+1) = \omega_{\min} + (\omega_{\max} - \omega_{\min}) \exp\left[-\frac{\theta \cdot t^2}{2 \cdot t_{\max}}\right] \quad (11)$$

The inertia weight ω is calculated at each iteration t using the initial and termination inertia weights, ω_{\max} and ω_{\min} , respectively, along with a new parameter θ , which controls the smoothness of the weight decay curve. The term t_{\max} represents the maximum number of iterations of the algorithm.

The learning factors are updated at each iteration t , as shown in Eq. (12) and Eq. (13).

$$c_1 = c_{1-\max} - \frac{c_{1-\max} - c_{1-\min}}{t_{\max}^2} \cdot t^2 \quad (12)$$

$$c_2 = c_{2-\min} - \frac{c_{2-\max} - c_{2-\min}}{t_{\max}^2} \cdot t^2 \quad (13)$$

The adaptive particle evolution begins with higher weights and learning factors to encourage exploration and gradually decreases, promoting convergence towards the best global solution. The position (Eq. (1)) is updated using the nearest value of the sum of the current position and velocity. The velocity is updated using Eq. (2). To prevent particles from getting trapped at boundaries, a circular search space is used. Thus, when a particle moves beyond one boundary, it re-enters the search space from the opposite limit, effectively enabling continuous position updates. The approach can limit real-world applicability by oversimplifying deployment topologies and constraints (e.g., geographical zones).

E. Fitness Function

We introduced a fitness function (Eq. (14)) that evaluates the suitability of allocating a component to a cluster by balancing local resource utilisation and latency reduction. max_cpu and max_ram were set to 95% and 90%, requiring at least 5% free CPU and 10% free RAM on each cluster. Values below these thresholds are considered invalid, rendering the solutions infeasible. These parameter values are based on empirical experience and operational limits commonly adopted in industry to prevent resource exhaustion and maintain system responsiveness [12].

$$f(m_j, c_i) = \begin{cases} -\infty & \text{if infeasible} \\ 1 + w_1 \cdot R + w_2 \cdot L + w_p \cdot P & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Where m_j represents component j , c_i represents cluster i , and w_1 , w_2 , and w_p are weighting coefficients, and R measures the equilibrium between different resource utilisations (RAM, CPU, and storage) (Eq. (15)). The resource usage proportions are calculated using Eq. (17), where x and y represent $\langle ram, cpu, disk \rangle$. This term encourages a balanced use of resources, achieving a maximum score of 1 when the usage of all resource types is equal.

$$R = 1 - \frac{\Delta_{ram,cpu} + \Delta_{ram,disk} + \Delta_{cpu,disk}}{3} \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta_{x,y} = |r_x - r_y| \quad (16)$$

$$r_x = \frac{m_j.replicas \times m_j.x}{c_i.total_x} \quad (17)$$

Additionally, terms L and P are used to guide optimisation. In Eq. (18), L measures the satisfaction of component collocation constraints by encouraging interdependent components to be placed within the same cluster.

$$L = \sum_{m \in C_j} (x_m = k_i) \quad (18)$$

Where C_j denotes the set of components co-located with component c_j , and x_m representing the cluster assigned to component m , this term counts the number of satisfied collocation constraints for a given placement. Whereas P (Eq. (19)) serves as a penalty term that discourages placements resulting in insufficient available resources within a cluster, thereby ensuring the allocation remains feasible concerning resource capacity.

$$P = -\left(\frac{ram_penalty + cpu_penalty}{2}\right) \quad (19)$$

Resource penalties $ram_penalty$ and $cpu_penalty$ apply when available RAM or CPU drops below thresholds ram_thr and cpu_thr , set by 90% and 95%. Penalties are normalised relative to total resource capacity, providing a quantifiable measure of resource scarcity.

IV. EVALUATION

We compared RALA-PSO with two state-of-the-art SI algorithms for a fair swarm-based evaluation, adding a non-AI greedy Spread method as a baseline. ML/RL methods, while relevant, were excluded for consistency. The evaluation (Figure 1) employed these algorithms to optimise the placement of a reference application across clusters and assess its impact in terms of (1) resource efficiency, (2) network transmission overhead, and (3) algorithm computation time. All algorithms were tested under identical conditions, replicating data and metrics from prior studies [3], [4]. RALA-PSO settings are summarised in Table I. The reference application, comprising 17 microservices, was sourced from the Alibaba Cluster TraceV2018 dataset [13], which provides normalised data on resource usage and communication patterns for each component. Workloads, the number of application components submitted to the algorithm, were generated by scaling the number of application instances using a dimensionless factor (user request), ranging from 1.0 to 5.0 in increments of 0.5. This factor allows meaningful fractional values because the dataset's traces are normalised.

To evaluate algorithm robustness under varying infrastructure conditions, each workload configuration was executed 30 times using different search spaces, i.e., distinct sets of candidate clusters available for component placement. Each

Fig. 1. Overview of the evaluation setup: microservice components (left), RALA-PSO scheduling (center), and target cluster resources (right).

search space consisted of 100 clusters, with resource capacities drawn from predefined reference sets based on the Alibaba Cluster TraceV2018 dataset, $total_cpu$ and $total_disk \in \{100, 200, 400\}$, and $total_ram \in \{60, 120, 180\}$. Each experiment run was repeated 30 additional times to ensure statistical robustness. The experiments were conducted on commodity hardware, equipped with an Intel Core i7-10750H processor and 16 GB of RAM.

TABLE I
RALA-PSO PARAMETERS CONFIGURATION

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
max_cpu	0.95	c1_min	0.01
max_ram	0.90	c1_max	2.5
weights	[0.4, 0.5, 0.1]	c2_min	0.01
theta	3.4	c2_max	2.5
max_itr	120	w_max	0.7
t_max	100	w_min	0.5

Resource efficiency (Eq. (20)) measures the balance of resource use (CPU, RAM, and storage) across cluster nodes, calculated as the average of normalised pairwise resource usage differences. Whereas, the network transmission overhead (Eq. (21)) quantifies the communication cost incurred by the placement of components, reflecting the additional overhead introduced when dependent components are placed further apart across clusters.

$$local_lb = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (\Delta_{ram,cpu,j} + \Delta_{ram,dsk,j} + \Delta_{cpu,dsk,j})}{3n} \quad (20)$$

Where $\Delta_{x,y,j}$ denotes the resource usage difference between resources x and y on node j , with n being the total number of cluster nodes.

$$t_req(cont_i, cont_k^{type}) \cdot d_trans(cont_i, cont_k^{type}) \cdot Dist(cont_i, cont_k^{type}) \cdot PassTime(cont_i, cont_k^{type}) \quad (21)$$

Eq. (21) considers t_{req} and d_{tran} (from Eq. (9)) to calculate the total volume of data transmitted. The communication cost factors in the distance (d_{trans}) between clusters and the transmission time ($dist$). Internal communication values are assumed to be approximately equal to 1, giving them minimal impact, while external communication is set to 4 to reflect a higher cost. The algorithm computation time corresponds to the duration required to complete the placement decision from request submission.

A. Results and Discussion

The experimental results are summarised in Figures 2, 3, and 4, referring to network transmission overhead, resource efficiency, and algorithm computation time, respectively.

Fig. 2. Normalised network transmission overhead cost incurred when dependent components are placed further apart across clusters. Lower values indicate better performance.

At lower user request levels (1.0x to 2.0x), RALA-PSO yields network overhead costs of approximately 49K and 117K (normalised values), comparable to MOPPSO-CMS's 25K and 95K. Nevertheless, as the workload increases, RALA-PSO outperforms the remaining. Notably, at the peak workload (5x), MOPPSO-CMS's network transmission cost rises to 430K, approximately 1.8 times worse than RALA-PSO's 237K. ACO-CMS and Spread exhibit even poorer scalability, both exceeding 500K under high load conditions. RALA-PSO's lower network overhead results from modelling inter-component communication, mainly through its co-location strategy, which incorporates dependencies during both initialisation and evolution. The overhead at low request volumes occurs because dependency and resource factors are equally weighted; with fewer active components, resource optimisation dominates, leading to more dispersed placements and more communication cost.

Fig. 3. Normalised resource utilisation balance across cluster nodes (CPU, RAM, storage). Lower values indicate better performance.

MOPPSO-CMS demonstrates superior performance in balancing resources, achieving the lowest resource utilisation values across all workloads, from 0.018 at 1.0 \times to 0.105 at 5.0 \times . RALA-PSO and ACO-CMS follow a similar trend, with RALA-PSO reaching 0.126 and ACO-CMS 0.129 at the peak workload (5.0 \times), while Spread performs the worst, peaking at 0.138. The slightly reduced resource efficiency of RALA-PSO reflects a design trade-off between minimising network costs and optimising resource use, making it well-suited for multi-objective optimisation, where competing goals must be balanced. RALA-PSO lowers network costs by co-locating dependent microservices, excelling in latency-sensitive, communication-heavy environments where minimizing inter-service traffic matters more than balanced resource use. Algorithm computation time indicates both efficiency and practical usefulness, with lower values signifying better performance. RALA-PSO overall delivered faster execution times, rising gradually from 2.59 to 5.91 seconds as the workload increased. Its lightweight design and efficient use of NumPy (e.g by using vectorised operations) translate to lower computational overhead, enabling rapid and scalable scheduling, key for dynamic cloud-native environments. Additionally, dynamic environments may require frequent re-invocation, which is enabled by RALA-PSO's low computational overhead.

Fig. 4. Algorithm runtime (in seconds) to compute placement decisions. Lower values indicate better performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented RALA-PSO, a novel SI-based scheduling algorithm designed for the demands of dynamic, cloud-native environments. RALA-PSO extends the widely known and well-established PSO algorithm, which is valued for its simplicity, flexibility, and effectiveness in solving multi-objective optimisation problems. To adapt PSO for microservice scheduling, RALA-PSO introduces several key modifications. RALA-PSO was evaluated using the Alibaba Cluster TraceV2018 dataset and benchmarked against state-of-the-art scheduling methods, MOPPSO-CMS and ACO-CMS. Experimental results demonstrate that RALA-PSO reduces network transmission overhead under increasing workloads, improves runtime efficiency, and maintains competitive resource

utilisation efficiency. These results underscore the effectiveness of RALA-PSO's PSO-based enhancements, which enable context-aware, resource-efficient scheduling under cloud-native constraints. By modelling communication patterns and feasibility directly in the optimisation process, RALA-PSO achieves a balanced trade-off between performance, feasibility, and execution time. The evaluation was limited to the Alibaba Cluster Trace V2018 dataset, and comparisons focused solely on SI-based schedulers to ensure a fair assessment against methods with similar optimisation dynamics. Future work should extend the analysis to additional datasets and include machine-learning and reinforcement-learning schedulers for a broader comparison.

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